

youth
SKILLS

Vulnerabilities and digital skills: Interactive report on the in-depth studies

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DISSEMINATION LEVEL

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You can read the interactive online report [here](#).

With the contribution of:

Study 1

Digital skills practices in non-formal learning context

Giovanna Mascheroni, Eva Eriksson, Bieke Zaman, Davide Cino, Silke Brandsen and Natalie Bressa.

Study 2

Refugee children and adolescents

Myria Georgiou, Leen d'Haenens, Veronica Donoso, Emilie Bossens and Alia Zaki.

Study 3

Adolescents experiencing mental health difficulties

Sonia Livingstone, Mariya Stoilova, Line Indrevoll Stänicke, Reidar Schei Jessen, Richard Graham, Elisabeth Staksrud and Tine Jensen.

Study 4

Recognising mis- and disinformation

Joyce Vissenberg, Marie Bedrošová and Guna Spurava.